

Retrospective Study of Functional Outcome of Core Decompression in Avascular Necrosis of Hip Upto Ficat-Arlet Stage IIbNeeraj Mahajan¹, Pawan Jakhar², Aakash Deep³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Jammu²Post-graduate Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Jammu³Post-graduate Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Jammu

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 25-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Aakash Deep

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Osteonecrosis, also known as avascular necrosis (AVN), is a debilitating disease characterized by the death of bone tissue due to an inadequate blood supply. Due to its intricate vascular supply and significant mechanical stress, the hip is especially prone to AVN. The goal of core decompression is to halt the progression of AVN, reduce pain, and avoid the need for more extensive surgery.**Material and Methods:** This prospective interventional study was carried out on patients of Avascular Necrosis of Femoral Head Ficat-Arlet Stage II in Department of Orthopaedics GMC Jammu over a period of 6 months. 20 patients were enrolled for the study which was followed up post-operatively at 1 month, 3 months & 6 months.**Results:** Out of a total of 20 enrolled patients, 12 were male while 8 were females. Right hip was involved in 45% of patients, left hip in 35%, while AVN was bilateral in 20% of the cases. The mean VAS score was 6.9 preoperatively and 3.9 at six months postoperatively.**Conclusion:** Core decompression is a promising procedure for pain relief for AVN grade 2 (Ficat-Arlet). However long term follow up is required and more studies with larger sample size will be required.**Keywords:** AVN Hip, Core decompression, Ficat-Arlet stage II.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Osteonecrosis, also known as avascular necrosis (AVN), is a debilitating disease characterized by the death of bone tissue due to an inadequate blood supply. The hip joint is one of the most often impacted regions, and AVN can cause severe discomfort, decreased range of motion (ROM), and eventually, joint dysfunction. [1] Due to its intricate vascular supply and significant mechanical stress, the hip is especially prone to AVN. While AVN might be difficult to diagnose in its early stages because of its asymptomatic nature, when the problem worsens, significant joint degeneration may occur. [2] The two main surgical procedures that have become more popular in treating AVN of the hip are total hip arthroplasty (THA) and core decompression. Core decompression reduces the pressure in the bone, opens up the hardening zone that hinders the repair of osteonecrosis, stimulates the formation of blood vessels around the decompression tunnel, enhances the replacement of the new bone, and delays the progression of osteonecrosis. [3] The goal of core decompression is to halt the progression of AVN, reduce pain, and avoid the need for more extensive surgery. This

procedure is particularly beneficial when AVN is diagnosed in its early stages.

According to US data, AVN is associated with alcohol use in 20%–40%, steroid treatment in 35%–40%, and idiopathic etiologies in 35%–40% of the cases. [4] The disease mostly affects young active individuals between the ages of 30 and 50 years. [5] It is bilateral in 30%–70% of the cases.

Aims & Objectives: To analyse functional outcomes of core decompression in patients with Avascular necrosis of Hip (Ficat-Arlet stage II).

Material & Method

This prospective interventional study was carried out on patients of Avascular Necrosis of Femoral Head Ficat-Arlet Stage II in Department of Orthopaedics GMC Jammu over a period of 6 months. A total of 25 patients were taken out of which 3 refused to take part in the study and 2 did not meet the inclusion criteria. Finally, 20 patients were enrolled for the study which was followed up post-operatively at 1 month, 3 months & 6 months. Functionally, patients were followed up with

preoperative and postoperative Harris Hip Scores and Visual Analog Scale (VAS).

Table 1: Ficat–Arlet staging system

Stage	Radiological findings
I	Plain radiograph, magnetic resonance imaging, and scintigraphy normal
IIA	Sclerotic and cystic lesion (absence of subchondral cystic formation)
IIB	Subchondral collapse (crescent sign) and/or subchondral aliasing
III	Irregular femoral contour
IV	Collapse of the femoral head, acetabular involvement, and articular destruction (osteoarthritis)

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18-60 years
- Patients with Avascular necrosis of Femoral Head upto Ficat Arlet Stage IIB

Exclusion Criteria

- Ficat Arlet stage III and IV
- Previous infection of hip joint
- Refusal for surgery

Operative Procedure

The patient is placed under regional anaesthesia and is then prepared and draped in an aseptic manner. Under fluoroscopic guidance, area of osteonecrosis is visualised. A guide wire is placed with an entry point laterally, but superior to the lesser trochanter medially to hit the affected area. Once it is determined that the guide wire is in the lesion, the area is drilled and cortical windows made with care not to penetrate the femoral head nor to violate the articular cartilage. A core of bone is removed from the lesion, the wound is closed in

layers, and a sterile dressing is applied. Following surgery, patients are discharged home on 5th post-op day and are kept non-weight bearing for about 3 months till healing is visualised on follow-up radiographs. Patients are taught strengthening exercises and educated to avoid high impact activities for 1 year.⁽⁶⁾

Results

Out of a total of 20 enrolled patients, 12 were male while 8 were females. Right hip was involved in 45% of patients, left hip in 35%, while AVN was bilateral in 20% of the cases. The mean VAS score was 6.9 preoperatively and 3.9 at six months postoperatively. The average time from admission to surgery was 4 days. Post operatively antibiotics were administered for 5 days and patient was then discharged. All patients were immobilized for 3 months postoperatively. Dressings were done on the first, third, and fifth postoperative days. Physiotherapy started on day one which included knee mobilization, static quadriceps exercises, ankle pump, and toe movement.

Table 2: Etiology/Risk factors for avascular necrosis of the femoral head

Etiology	Patients
Idiopathic	9
Steroid	4
Alcohol	7

Fig. 1: Pre-operative radiograph

Fig. 2: Post-operative radiograph

Fig. 3: 6 months post-op range of motion

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to Ficat-Arlet staging

Stage	No. of patients
I	4
IIA	7
IIB	9

Table 4: Harris Hip Score

Degree	Pre-op	At 6 months
< 70	8	3
71-80	5	2
81-90	7	6
>90	0	9

Fig 4: Pre-op MRI

Fig 5: Post-op radiograph

Fig. 6: 6 months post-op range of motion

Table 5: Visual Analog Scale score preoperatively and at six months postoperatively

VAS score	Pre-operative	6 months post-op
0-3	0	10
4-6	11	6
7-9	9	4

Discussion

Femoral head has a tenuous blood supply and thus even a slight vascular injury may lead to development of avascular necrosis of femoral head. In cases with AVN there is a rise in intra-osseous pressure within the femoral head.

Many different etiologies are involved in osteonecrosis of hip. Traumatic causes include femoral neck fracture or dislocation, while bulk of non-traumatic etiologies is made of chronic steroid use or alcohol consumption. [7]

Core decompression by decreasing the intra-osseous pressure within the femoral head can arrest or even reverse the process of osteonecrosis. Core decompression is the procedure of choice in the management of osteonecrosis of the femoral head of stage 2 before the onset of mechanical collapse. It does not have a role at a later stage when the sphericity of the femoral head is not maintained and other procedures such as rotational osteotomy or replacement arthroplasty needs to be done according to the stage of the disease and the extent of involvement of the head. [9,10]

Our study showed a male preponderance which is similar to the results reported by Bhabulkar et al where 81.25% of patients were male.[16]

In our study, the most common stage of presentation was Ficat-Arlet IIB.

Our study found a significant improvement in VAS scores which was similar to that reported by Sharma D, Javheri M, Patel U et al in their study on 50 hips with AVN Ficat-Arlet stage 2 managed with core decompression wherein they concluded that 45 patients had immediate post-operative pain relief. [8]

Therefore, our study suggests that core decompression in early stages of osteonecrosis of hip can help provide relief from pain, delay the

progression of AVN, avoid collapse, and improve functional outcomes in short term.

Conclusion

Core decompression is a promising procedure for pain relief for AVN grade 2 (Ficat-Arlet). However long term follow up is required and more studies with larger sample size will be required.

Bibliography

1. Szaro P, Geijer M, Solidakis N: Traumatic and non-traumatic bone marrow edema in ankle MRI: a pictorial essay. *Insights Imaging*. 2020, 11:97
2. Mont MA, Hungerford DS: Non-traumatic avascular necrosis of the femoral head. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*. 1995, 77:459-74.
3. Goker B, Block JA: Risk of contralateral avascular necrosis (AVN) after total hip arthroplasty (THA) for nontraumatic AVN. *Rheumatol Int*. 2006, 26:215-9
4. Bradway JK, Morrey BF. The natural history of the silent hip in bilateral atraumatic osteonecrosis. *J Arthroplasty* 1993; 8:383-7.
5. Lieberman JR, Berry DJ, Mont MA, Aaron RK, Callaghan JJ, Rajadhyaksha AD, et al. Osteonecrosis of the hip: management in the 21st century. *Instr Course Lect* 2003; 52:337-55.
6. Pierce TP, Jauregui JJ, Elmallah RK, Lavernia CJ, Mont MA, Nace J. A current review of core decompression in the treatment of osteonecrosis of the femoral head. *Curr Rev Musculoskelet Med*. 2015 Sep
7. Baig SA, Baig MN. Osteonecrosis of the Femoral Head: Etiology, Investigations, and Management. *Cureus*. 2018 Aug 21
8. Sharma D, Jhaveri M, Patel U et al Pain relief with core decompression and autologous bone graft in osteonecrosis of femoral head in grade 2. *Int J Orthop Sci* 2019
9. Smith SW, Fehring TK, Griffin WL, Beaver WB. Core decompression of the osteonecrotic

- femoral head. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* [Review]. 1995; 77(5):674-80.
10. Tan Y, He H, Wan Z, Qin J, Wen Y, Pan Z, Wang H, Chen L. Study on the outcome of patients with aseptic femoral head necrosis treated with percutaneous multiple small-diameter drilling core decompression: a retrospective cohort study based on magnetic resonance imaging and equivalent sphere model analysis. *J Orthop Surg Res.* 2020 Jul
 11. Brown TD, Pedersen DR, Baker KJ, Brand RA. Mechanical consequences of core drilling and bone grafting on osteonecrosis of the femoral head. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1993
 12. Mont MA, Ragland PS, Etienne G. Core decompression of the femoral head for osteonecrosis using percutaneous multiple small-diameter drilling. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2004 Dec
 13. Marciniak D, Furey C, Shaffer JW. Osteonecrosis of the femoral head. A study of 101 hips treated with vascularized fibular grafting. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2005 Apr
 14. Tetik C, Başar H, Bezer M, Erol B, Ađır I, Esemeli T. Comparison of early results of vascularized and non-vascularized fibular grafting in the treatment of osteonecrosis of the femoral head. *Acta Orthop Traumatol Turc.* 2011
 15. Babhulkar S: Osteonecrosis of femoral head: treatment by core decompression and vascular pedicle grafting. *Indian J Orthop.* 2009